

Additional file 2: Figure S1. Sliding window plot of global *P. vivax* *etrap* nucleotide diversity (Pi). A window length of 10bp and a step size of 5bp were used. The nucleotide diversity (Pi) of each population is plotted against the nucleotide position (x-axis). Nucleotide positions are those of the Sal I strain. Papua New Guinea, with only four samples, and Thailand with only one allele, were excluded from the analysis.

